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(Collaborative Network for European Clinical Trials For Children)

WP5 – Data coordinating
centre and data quality
standards

D5.5 Recommendations on how to 'FAIR-ify' eCRF data

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Table of Contents

Glossary.....	4
Abstract.....	7
1. Background.....	8
1.1. The FAIR data principles and their relevance to paediatric trial data.....	8
2. Recommendations on how to FAIRify eCRF data	10
2.1. High-level approach to FAIRification.....	10
3. Resources developed by c4c to increase FAIRness of paediatric clinical trial data	13
3.1 Cross Cutting Paediatric Data Dictionary	13
3.2. Clinical Data Modelling Tool.....	14
3.3. Recommendations on data standardisation and harmonisation of terminology.....	15
3.4. Therapeutic Area User Guide (TAUG) for Paediatrics	16
3.5. Raising awareness of the importance of Semantic Interoperability	16
4. Resources promoted by c4c to increase FAIRness of paediatric clinical trial data.....	17
4.1. Repositories	17
4.2. FAIRPlus	18
4.3. ECRIN Metadata Repository	18
4.4 Rare 2030 Policy Recommendations.....	19
4.5. EURORDIS data collection to illustrate patient perspectives on data sharing and protection	21
4.6. Select existing initiatives and papers	21
5. Next Steps	22

Glossary

Term	Acronym	Description
Accessible	A	The ease and conditions under which data can be obtained.
Case Report Form	CRF	A printed, optical, or electronic document designed to record all of the protocol required information to be reported to the sponsor on each trial subject. A CRF is generally used to record data which are copied from source documents. However, the CRF can sometimes be the first and only document where data items are recorded. When the CRF is the source document for any item of data, this needs to be clearly identified in the protocol (ICH-GCP, section 6.4.9)(1,2).
Clinical Data Acquisition Standards Harmonization	CDASH	A CDISC standard that establishes a standard way to collect data consistently across studies and sponsors so that collection formats and structures provide clear traceability of submissions into the Study Data Tabulation Model (SDTM), delivering more transparency to regulators and others who conduct data review.
Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium	CDISC	A standards developing organization dealing with medical research data linked with healthcare, to "enable information system interoperability to improve medical research and related areas of healthcare" https://www.cdisc.org/ . Third party of UNEW in c4c.
Clinical Modelling Tool		A tool to facilitate modelling of clinical data (see data modelling)
Cross Cutting Paediatric Data Dictionary	CCPDD	The data dictionary under development by c4c to map commonly occurring data items in paediatric clinical trials
Data Modelling		Capturing and organising data elements in a meaningful way so that they can be stored and utilised by computer systems
Digital Asset		Exists in a digital format and comes with the right to use.
Electronic Case Report Form	eCRF	An electronic version of a case report form – an auditable electronic record of information generally reported to the sponsor on each trial subject, according to a clinical investigation protocol. The eCRF enables clinical investigation data to be systematically captured, reviewed, managed, stored, analysed, and reported.
Electronic Data Capture System	EDC	Electronic data capture is the process of collecting clinical trial data into a permanent electronic form. An EDC system uses technology to streamline the collection and transmission of

		clinical trial data from the patient to the data warehouse.
Electronic Health Record	EHR	The collection of patient and population electronically stored health information in a digital format. EHRs can be shared across different health care settings.
European Reference Network	ERN	European Reference Networks (ERNs) are virtual networks involving healthcare providers across Europe. They aim to facilitate discussion on complex or rare diseases and conditions that require highly specialised treatment, and concentrated knowledge and resources.
FAIR Data Working Group		A c4c working group made up of FAIR data experts from within the c4c consortium.
FAIRPlus		An IMI project that aims to increase the discovery, accessibility and reusability of data from selected Innovative Medicine Initiative (IMI) projects, as well as internal data from pharmaceutical industry partners. It will also organise training for data scientists in academia, SMEs and pharmaceutical companies to enable wider adoption of best practises in life science data management.
Findable	F	The ease with which online information can be found by a user.
Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable	FAIR	FAIR data are data which meet principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability
General Data Protection Regulation	GDPR	A data protection and privacy law in the European Union and the European Economic Area. REGULATION (EU) 2016/679 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)
Innovative Medicines Initiative	IMI	An EU public-private partnership funding health research and innovation
Interoperable	I	Computer systems or software can exchange and make use of information between devices made by different manufacturers
International Organization for Standardization EN 13606	ISO EN 13606	European Standard for an information architecture to communicate Electronic Health Records (EHR) of a patient.
Kawasaki Disease Coronary Artery Aneurysm Prevention trial	KD-CAAP	One of the c4c PoV studies. A multi-centre, randomised trial of corticosteroids plus standard of care treatment versus standard of care treatment alone to prevent heart complications in

		Kawasaki disease. KD-CAAP provided their CRFs for a use case for this deliverable.
Metadata		A set of data that describes and gives information about other data
National Cancer Institute Enterprise Vocabulary Service	NCI EVS	<p>Since 1997, NCI Enterprise Vocabulary Services (EVS) has provided terminology content, tools, and services to accurately code, analyse and share cancer and biomedical research, clinical and public health information.</p> <p>Paediatric Terminology: The National Institute of Child Health and Human Development (NICHD) and EVS are working with numerous contributors from national and international academic, clinical and research institutions to provide standardized terminology for coding paediatric clinical trials and other research activities.</p>
Nomenclatures		A system of names or terms used in a specialist field.
Ontology		An explicit formal specification of how to represent relationships among objects, concepts, and other entities that belong to a particular domain of experience or knowledge
Paediatric Data Interoperability Working Group	PDIWG	A c4c working group which reviews and advises c4c WP5 on the technical requirements needed to ensure data interoperability
Proof of Viability Study	PoV study	A set of clinical studies from different Sponsors (industry or non-industry), across different therapeutic areas and different age groups that will test the viability of the c4c network.
Real World Clinical Data	RWD	Clinical data from sources other than traditional clinical trials
Registry		A collection of data related to patients with a specific diagnosis, condition, or procedure.
Repository		A central location for storing and managing data.
Reusable	R	The use of research data for a research activity or purpose other than that for which it was originally intended.
Semantic Interoperability		Allows computer systems to exchange data with unambiguous, shared meaning
Study Data Tabulation Model	SDTM	CDISC standard for organising and formatting data to streamline processes in collection, management, analysis and reporting
Therapeutic Area User Guide	TAUG	Extend the CDISC Foundational Standards to represent data that pertains to specific disease areas.

Abstract

The FAIR data principles aim to improve the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse of digital assets¹.

The c4c FAIR Data Working Group was formed to ascertain the *relevance* of the FAIR principles to the domain of paediatric clinical trial data. The working group is exploring the potential of each FAIR principle - theoretically - for interoperable data sharing and (metadata-level) data querying between Electronic Case Report Forms (eCRFs) from different studies. The emphasis of this work is to focus on enabling FAIR data collection from the planning stages of a trial. The working group will also consider the potential for greater interoperability between eCRFs and the broader field of electronic health records (EHRs) and real-world clinical data.

This deliverable, in its current form, sets out the rationale for this work and the *process* needed to FAIRify a CRF. To this end of creating eCRFs from the start, the FAIR Data Working Group is analysing CRFs from the KD-CAAP Proof of Viability (PoV) Study as a pilot study to develop a practical guide for all stakeholders interested in paediatric research data, which will be elaborated as part of a future update to the deliverable.

The working group will use data items from the CRFs as examples to identify how and where the FAIR data principles could be applied. For instance, recommending that certain types of data collected through the eCRF - e.g. lab data - could benefit from being captured using particular international nomenclatures.

This deliverable sets out the added value of applying the FAIR principles to paediatric data and sets out a plan for developing practical recommendations. The deliverable also describes how existing resources, developed both within c4c and external to the consortium can also be used to make the data collected within c4c more FAIR.

¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

1. Background

1.1. The FAIR data principles and their relevance to paediatric trial data

The FAIR data principles², as mentioned above, contain guidelines to improve the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of *digital assets*. They were developed to improve machine-actionability, referring to the capability of computational systems to find, access, interoperate and reuse data without human intervention. The computational support increases the volume, complexity and overall speed of data exchange and interpretation: attempting to manually combine datasets from different projects or studies, without the use of computational support, is incredibly time-consuming. The FAIR data principles help to build an ecosystem in which data is more easily shared, exchanged, pooled or queried. This includes metadata, data and supporting infrastructure (e.g. search engines).

In the current COVID public health emergency, FAIR principles have proven to be very useful. The Virus Outbreak Detection Network (VODAN)³ and [Zenodo](#) are examples of networks applying at least some of the FAIR data principles from the start.

In recent years, the FAIR principles⁴ have gained prominence in many communities, and have been endorsed by entities such as [ELIXIR](#) (the European Research Infrastructure for Data), [BBMRI](#) (the ESFRI for biobanking), the [European Open Science Cloud](#), [FORCE11](#), [NIH](#) through its 'commons' program, and the [G20](#). The European Commission and funders see the relevance of the FAIR data principles. IMI is funding several FAIR-related projects.⁵

The FAIR principles have been increasingly embraced by the rare disease community; for instance, there is a [GO-FAIR implementation network](#) for rare disease, intended to oversee activities relating to FAIR data in this broad field. The benefits here are clear: in areas where patient data is scarce, knowledge generation and enhanced research capacity often depends upon the ability to collect and pool data from as many patients as possible, based on commonalities of diagnosis, of clinical presentation, of treatment regimens, etc. Collecting data in a standardised manner (for example, with diseases coded according to the same nomenclature, lab reports generated in accordance with the same reporting standards, clinical terms harmonised, etc) will allow it to become more syntactically and semantically interoperable, which increases the power of that data in several ways. Significant attention has been paid to making rare disease data more FAIR; indeed, the FAIR principles have been highlighted as a Recognised Resource⁶ by the [IRDiRC](#) (International Rare Disease Research Consortium). Initially, these efforts largely focused on facilitating diagnostics by connecting genotype and phenotype data with available bio samples: a good example of this is the [RD-Connect Genome Phenome Analysis Platform](#). A set of recommendations were produced to

² <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

³ <https://www.digitalscholarship.leiden.nl/articles/fair-datas-cutting-edge> and <https://www.go-fair.org/implementation-networks/overview/vodan/>

⁴ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

⁵ HARMONY <https://www.harmony-alliance.eu/> Open PHACTS <https://www.openphactsfoundation.org/> EMIF <http://www.emif.eu/> BigData@Heart <https://www.bigdata-heart.eu/> ROADMAP <https://roadmap-alzheimer.org/> PIONEER <https://prostate-pioneer.eu/> FAIRPlus <https://fairplus-project.eu/>

⁶ <https://irdirc.org/research/irdirc-recognized-resources/>

explore the relevance of FAIR data to the virtual care activities of the 24 ERNs (European Reference Networks).⁷ Significant attention has also been paid to making registry data more FAIR (see section 4.6).

The c4c FAIR data WG seeks to draw on these experiences from the rare disease field, given the fact that many paediatric conditions are rare, and explore what FAIR might mean when applied to a relatively new data domain, namely clinical trial data.

For paediatric trials, applying FAIR-principles is of great importance. Often the number of patients enrolled in paediatric trials is small, making the data scarce and valuable. Due to the specific hurdles in paediatric medicine development, many paediatric studies are international, multi-site trials, making the need for interoperability of data between different investigators and sites even more important.

For paediatric trials, the disease being studied is often in rare, further increasing recruiting difficulty and multicentric designs. Once a trial has been completed - or indeed has failed - that data may remain incredibly useful for a number of purposes. Such datasets could function as a source of longitudinal natural history and observational data, enabling insights that might reduce the number of actual clinical trials that are needed, or could reduce their required sample size or make the targeting of eligible patients more accurate. There is also interesting potential in avoiding or limiting the use of placebo arms in studies, which can be challenging in paediatric populations. Furthermore, pharmacokinetic data from clinical trials can be pooled. In theory, data from completed or failed trials may be used to explore the association between treatment regimens and clinical outcomes.

If historic clinical trial data can be discovered, shared, and reused, as a result of it being well documented and interoperable, then this may ultimately decrease the number of patients needed for new clinical trials, and potentially reduce the cost and effort of conducting those trials. Moreover, reuse of digital assets is especially crucial in a paediatric setting, decreasing the burden on young patients and their families, increasing the value of research on a retrospective basis.

The experience of organisations and projects that make their data FAIR is that it is more challenging and effort-intensive if done **retrospectively**. It is much easier to set up a data dictionary and data representation using standards at the outset, and to document metadata on a continual basis.

Moreover, during the clinical research process, FAIR data guarantees that data are well organised, easy to use and with long-lasting usability to facilitate the analysis and reporting of safety and other clinical trial data for regulatory purposes. Additionally, the principles make data easily understandable by investigators and clinical research professionals involved in clinical trials from different countries and/or regions facilitating different levels of interoperability and sharing.

It is important to emphasise that exploring the sorts of steps necessary to make paediatric clinical trial data more FAIR does not infer any obligations on actors engaged in sponsoring clinical trials. Rather, c4c recognises that, for the reasons above, sharing data - or otherwise imbuing it with the power to serve a

⁷ <http://www.rd-action.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/05/Recommended-Practices-for-Data-Standardisation-in-the-Context-of-the-operation-of-ERNs-final-2017.pdf>

secondary purpose, of some sort - is increasingly a priority of many organisations and researchers.⁸ Even if a sponsor does not have a clear vision of if and how they may wish to share and reuse their study data, it makes sense, strategically, to optimally prepare trial data from the outset and build these practices into the data collection, in order to render it more interoperable down the line. This is essentially a move towards future-proofing data and limiting the need for time-consuming manual cross-mapping and curation of the data at a point in the future. Furthermore, also applying the FAIR principles to real-world clinical and consumer data, be it collected manually or using professional or consumer devices such as activity trackers, eases their incorporation in clinical trials. This is important for c4c as the use of wearables and other biosensors is rapidly accelerating in clinical research⁹.

This guide has therefore been developed to promote and support the proactive FAIR-ification of CRFs, which is an important ingredient of preparing data to be shareable and smoothly reusable from the outset.

2. Recommendations on how to FAIRify eCRF data

Making eCRF data FAIR involves a more or less fixed set of activities, each of which requires decisions to be made. This chapter first addresses these steps at a high level, relating them to the FAIR aspects, and then discusses each of the steps in more detail. It is important to realise that for many aspects there may either be multiple viable choices, or a lack of established options, meaning that the FAIR community has not yet developed best practices. This is in keeping with the innovative and exploratory nature of this work.

2.1. High-level approach to FAIRification

Describe the dataset (Findability + Accessibility).

Similar to a book cover describing author, title, publisher, and a summary, a dataset should be described: the author and/or steward of the dataset; the study subject profile of the dataset; and the criteria for inclusion / exclusion of data in / from the dataset. It is important to realise that interpretation of this information should require as little knowledge as possible upfront, so no assumptions should be made about prior knowledge of the queries - whether of a person or computer - that will be searching for the data set. For example, people (or machines) need to know, understand or be able to infer whether a dataset is about persons, patients (and which kinds of patients), cases (and with which diseases), countries, drugs, or devices. This level of detail must be made explicit in the description of the dataset.

Apart from the general description, access conditions - including all limitations, obligations and permissions - need to be provided and described in a machine-readable way by converting the documentation into FAIR metadata to be processed in real time and to be checked against access requirements when asking for access to data. As FAIR data does not imply open data, a description needs to be provided as to if and how data can be accessed, especially by considering data protection obligations and applicable ethics and regulatory requirements. Such conditions may also concern temporal or geographic limitations and limitations on use. Further, the protocols, if any, via which the data can be accessed, should be described,

⁸ See for instance the recently-published *Recommendations from the Rare 2030 Foresight Study* - <https://www.rare2030.eu/recommendations/> - in particular pages 92 and 104, as outlined below in section 4.4.

⁹ to <https://www.fda.gov/science-research/science-and-research-special-topics/real-world-evidence>

provide authentication and authorisation mechanisms, and should be open and free.¹⁰ For instance, some datasets may only be visible within an organisational firewall, meaning the data cannot be downloaded or copied but only viewed within a secure system. It may be that no data can readily be viewed or accessed from a portal or repository at all, but rather a named contact holds the data and will themselves (alone or in a dedicated body) grant or deny access to individual researchers, providing they fulfil specific criteria (which, again, should -if seeking to respect those ‘accessibility’ principles- be clear to anyone seeking to access that data).

Describe contents of the dataset (Interoperability).

Complementing the description of the dataset as a whole, its contents need to be described as well. A “data dictionary” is required, that provides information about the data elements (i.e., the attributes) in the dataset, their data types, and aggregate information about the values of the data elements, such as a distribution of recorded values. So on a very basic level, if a researcher or other stakeholder wishes to obtain data from patients with Gaucher Disease, or from neonatal patients with microcephaly, or from Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy patients who take corticosteroids, they will need to see whether those patients/relationships actually feature in a particular dataset. If a researcher is seeking datasets pertaining to Juvenile Idiopathic Arthritis patients, general datasets on ‘Arthritis’, which were dominated by data from elderly patients, would not be helpful. As far as possible, the contents of a dataset should be captured in a standardised and harmonised form, for instance using agreed international nomenclatures to describe certain types of data. For example, this might be use of ATC codes for medicines; use of the [Human Phenotype Ontology](#) (HPO) to capture phenotype data; use of [LOINC](#) for lab data.

Deposit the description of the dataset and its contents (Findability).

Having a data description is not only useful to describe a given dataset, but also to select datasets based on the description. This requires the description being “advertised”, in order to be included in search results. Deposition of the description can (and in many cases will) be separate from any deposition of the actual data.

Process

Making a dataset FAIR is not a one-off single-step effort, but instead a continuous and cyclic process, driven by added value and feasibility.

Steps to FAIRification:

1. Gain a clear description of what the dataset pertains to (i.e., inclusion/exclusion criteria, end points, lab results etc.) and on the accessibility conditions. This point will contribute towards Findability and Accessibility. However, at this point there is little agreement about what exactly pertains to metadata for any dataset, unless it is very generic.
2. Triage the data points (discrete units of information) into “Must/Should/Could/Won’t FAIRify” (if items require explanation/clarification, the FAIRification team would either need to reach out to the CRF developers, or temporarily declare as “Could”)

¹⁰ See for instance Nsl, Data Intelligence. (2020). The “A” of FAIR -As Open as Possible, as Closed as Necessary. 2. 47-55. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/337972722_The_A_of_FAIR_-_As_Open_as_Possible_as_Closed_as_Necessary

3. Analyse Must/Should items, and see if and how they would need to be FAIRified (as-is, or with interpretation)
4. For all items to address (starting with “Must”): layout the overarching model and potential target vocabularies (e.g., CDISC)
5. Match items on models and vocabularies (i.e., standardise how data elements relate to one another, and make semantics of data elements and permitted values explicit by linking them to vocabularies), determine “problem areas” (e.g., non-matches to model and/or vocabularies)
6. Perform “rolling FAIRification”, via an established procedure to evaluate mappings, incrementally work through problematic mappings, and expand towards “Could” data elements, until no further FAIRification is possible.
7. Specify reuse conditions based on the models, vocabularies and mappings (matching fields from one database with another) used.

Some of these points are relatively straightforward to address but the c4c FAIR data WG has recognised some gaps and has therefore developed in more detail certain parts of the FAIRification solution.

Following the approval of this deliverable the FAIR Date WG of c4c, supported by a FAIRification squad from FAIRplus, will FAIRify a section (or all) of the KD-CAAP CRF. This will be a demonstration of the above workflow steps and help to guide the team on possible further explanatory material that would be useful to publish. Given the confidential nature of the KDCAAP CRF, that worked example cannot itself be included in future published material.

Development of a FAIR Implementation Profile¹¹

Implementation of the FAIR principles is driven by the standards adhered to in the domain of implementation. Together, these determine a set of implementation decisions, which is referred to as a FAIR implementation profile. For c4c recommendations, this profile will reflect adherence to domain-relevant standards for the paediatric clinical trial data community. See also principle R1.3.¹²

A challenge here, however, is that in many ways there is no clear consensus on the most relevant and appropriate standards to support reuse of data, as the concept of sharing or querying trial data is still relatively new. For the domain of clinical trials, the use of the CDISC-standards is important, due to the requirement from some regulators to submit data in CDISC standards. This means they are commonly used by companies. For the paediatric domain, two working groups were formed to establish standards/resources for the implementation profile: The Paediatric Data Interoperability Working Group (PDIWG), and the Cross-Cutting Paediatric Data Dictionary Working Group (CCPDD WG). The resulting resources are described below. In fact, one of these - the *Recommendations on Data Standardisation and Harmonization of Terminology* - is already, in a sense, an embryonic FAIR Implementation Profile for the paediatric clinical trial domain, as it constitutes a first attempt to agree some ‘good practices’ for handling paediatric trial data (see further section 3.3)

¹¹ <https://www.go-fair.org/how-to-go-fair/fair-implementation-profile/>
<https://osf.io/2p85g/>

¹² <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

3. Resources developed by c4c to increase FAIRness of paediatric clinical trial data

3.1 Cross Cutting Paediatric Data Dictionary

The c4c Cross Cutting Paediatric Data Dictionary (CCPDD) acts as a ‘lookup table’ of sorts, listing disease-agnostic paediatric data items that are commonly collected in clinical trials in neonatal, paediatric and/or adolescent studies. The CCPDD has already been used, in its early version (launched in 2019), by the three non-Industry PoV studies. The CCPDD items are grouped into the following areas:

- Demographics
- Vital Signs
- Pubertal Status
- Other

The data dictionary provides definitions of each item as well as suggested domains, qualifiers units and code lists. Where they exist, the CCPDD links to [CDISC standards](#); CDASH around data collection and SDTM around the tabulation of data.

CDISC mapped Item	recommended units (for example)	CDISC units (CDISC Codelist)	value range C-CODE	CDISC Evaluation
Height	cm, metres, inches, feet	cm (C49668) m (C41139) in (C48500) ft (C71253)	not needed	Vital signs test exists in CDISC CT (HEIGHT (C25347)) CDISC Definition "The vertical measurement or distance from the base to the top of an object; the vertical dimension of extension. (NCI)"
Total body Length	cm, inches, feet	cm (C49668) in (C48500) ft (C71253)	not needed	Vital signs test exists in CDISC CT (BODLNTH (C81298)) CHANGE DEFINITION: CDISC Definition "The linear extent in space from one end of the body to the other end, or the extent of the body from beginning to end." Consider (NCI C81298) "The total linear extent of the body

Figure 1: Extract from the CCPDD showing CDISC mapped items ‘Height’ and ‘Total body length’

CDISC mapped Item	CDISC SDTM Domain	CDISC Qualifier Variables	Guidance	Source of information CDASH = Data Collection SDTM = Data Tabulation
Height	Vital Signs (VS)	unit, standardised unit	Specify standardised unit	CDASHIG v2.0 - https://www.cdisc.org/standards/foundation/cdash/cdash-20#Bookmark256 SDTMIG v3.3 -
Total body Length	Vital Signs (VS)	Vital Signs Position of Subject (VSPOS)? - not needed if new definition accepted as it states "recumbent"	Specify standardised unit	CDASHIG v2.0 - https://www.cdisc.org/standards/foundation/cdash/cdash-20#Bookmark256 SDTMIG v3.3 - https://www.cdisc.org/standards/foundation

Figure 2: Extract from the CCPDD showing additional information for CDISC mapped items ‘Height’ and ‘Total body length’

Some of the new data items suggested by the working group were not included in the initial version which was expedited to be available for the PoV studies. Work has started on v2 of the CCPDD and it will include some of the more complex data items missing from v1, such as developmental scales.

By standardising at least, a core part of the data collected within paediatric trials, pooling such data between and across studies in the future may be easier, as the meaning of the data items is harmonised. The CCPDD should thus support FAIRification by making CRF data more interoperable and reusable.

3.2. Clinical Data Modelling Tool

The CCPDD is progressively accumulating a standardised set of data items with definitions, represented, as described above, on an Excel spreadsheet. However, the spreadsheet does not capture all of the structure and semantic specifications that are needed for an unambiguous and consistent adoption by multiple downstream actors. It does not offer any form of validation checking, for instance, to make sure entries are complete and internally consistent. It is poorly equipped to vision-manage changes and has no graphical presentation capability. An important limitation of an Excel version of the CCPDD is that anyone using it is required to transcribe the relevant content into their own eCRF-generating tools/their own data capture systems.

Several members of the PDIWG strongly recommended that future versions of the CCPDD should be constructed in a more formalised and multi-dimensional way to better support scalability and sustainability, and importantly, to enable computational adoption. After consultation with the Project Steering Committee and Project Leadership Team, a pilot was organised to test the use of a tool to test their recommendations.

A data dictionary modelling pilot project was consequently undertaken which sought to reproduce selected parts of the CCPDD v.1 using a particular example of a modelling tool: [Direcht](#). This tool has been developed by a team with a long history in the clinical modelling field within the health domain and conforms to ISO clinical modelling international standards.

An important consideration for c4c is the ability to represent the CCPDD in a tool using the CDISC [Operational Data Model \(ODM\)](#): this means that the contents of the dictionary can be imported into one or more of the EDC (electronic data capture) systems being used in the project. However, not all EDC systems use CDISC, so it was also important that any clinical data model could be viewed as 'standards agnostic' to optimise its applicability. The pilot team therefore chose to base the clinical data modelling tool on ISO EN 13606 as it is considered a semantics neutral format and is agnostic of the more specific implementation standards that are used in healthcare and in clinical research.

The clinical data modelling tool, as it stands, thus provides a standards-agnostic (but nonetheless standardised) data dictionary representation, which supports alternative export formats, such as those used in the wider healthcare domain.

A second pilot started in March 2021 to further test the functionality and usability of the tool to develop a full CCPDDv2. The pilot is expected to conclude Q2 of 2022.

The CCPDD in its current Excel format standardises the data collected within trials. The second stage of the pilot aims to demonstrate that non-data experts can use a data modelling tool to represent this data in a more formalised way which should further enhance FAIRification.

3.3. Recommendations on data standardisation and harmonisation of terminology

Contribution to FAIR: Findable, Interoperable, Reusable

In 2019, in order to provide some guidance and support to the non-Industry PoV studies in c4c, a set of data-focused Recommendations was produced. This was intended as a first version of this resource, to be further elaborated and enhanced across the c4c project lifespan.

The 2019 Recommendations (v 1) may be summarised as follows:

1. Use version 1 of the c4c CCPDD and user manual
2. Refer to the [paediatric terminology resource](#) curated by the NCI NICHD EVS for Adverse Events
3. Use NCI NICHD EVS as your primary resource if you are studying a condition included in the disease-area-specific terminology subsets
4. Code paediatric diseases, especially rare diseases, with appropriate diagnostic ontologies

The optimal means of implementing some of the FAIR recommendations is yet to be agreed; for instance, it is logical to consider that an important component of FAIRifying paediatric trial data is to allow would-be data accessors to find anonymised CRF level data for the particular conditions or symptoms they are interested in. If these are rare, it is generally expected that data should be annotated with the ontological form of the [Orphanet](#) nomenclature for disease classification (the Orpha Code, is deemed the most sensitive and granular nomenclature for rare diseases¹³).

This would support researchers seeking, for instance, data from studies in Limb Girdle Muscular Dystrophy, or indeed a specific subtype of this heterogeneous set of clinical conditions. Equally, however, should a researcher wish to expand their search to look at data from trials in muscular dystrophies in general (of which Limb-Girdle is just one family), capturing diagnoses using the Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology would presumably facilitate this, as it operates on a hierarchical structure and avoids the need to manually examine and map data. Having said this, diagnoses are typically not captured on an actual eCRF, but rather appear in the trial's main inclusion criteria. So how and where to record disease diagnoses, as an example, will need to be explored and addressed in future versions of this document, which, already constitutes an early FAIR Implementation Profile of sorts.

This resource was also summarised in D5.2 'Recommendations on CT documents archiving'

¹³ See for instance the European recommendations relating to modification: https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/health/files/rare_diseases/docs/recommendation_coding_cegrd_en.pdf. The Orphanet RD Ontology (ORDO) has also been recognised as an IRDiRC-Recognised resource - <https://irdirc.org/research/irdirc-recognized-resources>

3.4. Therapeutic Area User Guide (TAUG) for Paediatrics

Contribution to FAIR: Interoperable, Reusable

CDISC is a not-for-profit standards development organisation working to improve the clarity of data in clinical research by bringing together a global community of experts to develop and advance data standards of the highest quality. CDISC is involved in the c4c network as a third party to Newcastle University.

[Therapeutic Area User Guides \(TAUGs\)](#) extend the CDISC [Foundational Standards](#) to represent data that pertains to specific disease areas. TAUGs include disease-specific metadata, examples and guidance on implementing CDISC standards for a variety of uses, including global regulatory submissions.

Drawing on the consensus building approach used to deliver the initial version of the CCPDD, CDISC will use version two of the CCPDD (currently under development) in addition to the normal CDISC processes to develop the paediatric TAUG. Partners from c4c, and members of the c4c Expert groups are involved in this work. The development process started in January 2021 and has convened a group of experts to follow the CDISC Standards Development Process to identify the most relevant concepts for paediatric studies for inclusion in the TAUG. The paediatric TAUG will be published on the CDISC website in December 2022, where it will be freely available. The TAUG can be used to represent data in studies pertaining to paediatrics to expedite the regulatory review process, reduce time to market, and drive operational efficiencies within organisations that use them. As all global companies tend to use CDISC, this output should result in a wider body of paediatric-relevant data collected and represented in a more standardised and interoperable way.

3.5. Raising awareness of the importance of Semantic Interoperability

Contribution to FAIR: Interoperability

In terms of health data, semantic interoperability is about increasing the understanding and knowledge of diseases and health by making information and data available and interpretable by both humans and machines. Achieving semantic interoperability can bring a multitude of benefits to the healthcare field, including increased comprehension of medical terms and concepts, easy access and integration of patient records.

c4c was established to overcome the multitude of barriers to the conduction of efficient paediatric clinical trials. It is well acknowledged that there are not enough medicines designed specifically for the paediatric population, and that safety and efficacy data on the paediatric population is scarce. One route to better, faster, more streamlined clinical trials in paediatric diseases is an enhanced ability for data collected in disparate systems to be able to 'speak' other data. This could be CRF data collected in different clinical trials by the same sponsor; or CRF data from different studies led by different sponsors/CROs; or potentially CRF data linked somehow with Real World Data, such as EHRs or even registry data. Having access to natural history data and combining it better with laboratory data, could create more precise paediatric laboratory reference ranges for different age cohorts and/or indications impacting on our safety profiling. This would also be a major advantage for industry

There may generally be multiple ways of presenting information for example, through different ontologies, but with increasing alignment capabilities through resources such as [UMLS Metathesaurus](#), [BioPortal](#) and [Ontology Look-up Service](#) that may become less of a problem.

Achieving semantic interoperability, (in particular at the CRF level) is critical to achieving the Interoperability of the FAIR data principles.

To raise awareness of Semantic Interoperability within c4c WP5 have produced a number of recommendations and guides around the subject, as well as promoting the use of ontologies and controlled terminology to the PoV studies and wider consortium.

4. Resources promoted by c4c to increase FAIRness of paediatric clinical trial data

4.1. Repositories

In the framework of the Work Package 5 “*Data coordinating centre and data quality standards*” in task 5.4, a scouting exercise of the initiatives sharing clinical trial data - with a focus on paediatric data - was performed in 2018. Initiatives, such as platforms, projects, private and public repositories of pharma industries or non-profit organisations, consortia of Sponsors/Funders, databases of pharma industries or non-profit organisations were investigated. See also previous research carried out by the European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network (ECRIN)¹⁴

Eighteen initiatives were found, chosen for consideration due to their open data policies.

1. AllTrials campaign
2. Laboratory of Neuroimaging Image & Data Archive (IDA)
3. Biolecerate (Transcelerate)
4. NIDA
5. BioLINCC
6. National Sleep Research Resources (NSRR)
7. Therapeutics Development Network|CF Foundation (CF TDN)
8. Project Data Sphere (PDS)
9. ClinicalStudyDataRequest (CSDR)
10. Pfizer trial data and results
11. DASH (data and specimen hub)
12. Paediatric Trials Network (PTN)
13. DPUK
14. Swedish National Data Service
15. Duke and SOAR
16. Vivli
17. Fighshare
18. The YODA project

¹⁴ <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30876434/>

In 2021, an update of this activity has started and is aligned with the work of the c4c FAIR Data WG by focusing the discussions on how the FAIR principles relate to paediatric trial data. The activity will take the form of a structured survey with possible in-depth qualitative interviews. The work is aimed at investigating several aspects of each repository, as characteristics of data and documents collected, their paediatric specificity, legal provisions for accessing and reusing data, and IT technologies. Beside the main aims of the work, compliance of each initiative with the FAIR principles is going to be assessed as well.

This work is important, particularly for the 'F' and 'A' of FAIR. Activities to standardise data and harmonise terminology for secondary purposes makes more sense if undertaken as part of a broader strategy to actually encourage and enable trials to make that data available, under certain conditions, for future research - researchers need to know where they can find such data, and repositories are a natural source.

As the activities of tasks 5.2, 3, and 4 develop across the second half of the c4c initiative, questions such as the following will be addressed more closely:

- as above, what are the relative strengths of the repositories identified by task 5.4;
- how paediatric specific the repositories are, do they offer paediatric search terms, do they include data from paediatric studies?
- how easy are they for researchers to use, in terms of depositing and finding data they require;
- how FAIR are they at present; how might paediatric data deposited in these repositories be made more reuse-ready, both in terms of practical methods the study team could employ to make their data more FAIR and also in terms of how the repositories describe data about these collections (metadata);
- what is the best way for paediatric researchers to discover and/or use these sorts of repositories, where they wish to make closed or failed study data available more widely.

c4c will also need to consider how metadata repositories such as the ECRIN metadata platform (see below, section 4.3) play a key role here, and avoid the need to create new repositories or catalogues.

4.2. FAIRPlus

The [IMI2 FAIRplus](#) project aims to develop tools and guidelines for making life science data FAIR. FAIRPlus will be collaborating with c4c to share advice on the FAIRification of eCRFs as part of their remit to increase the discovery, accessibility and reusability of data from other IMI projects.

FAIRPlus are developing the [FAIR Cookbook](#) to collate protocols for making data FAIR and to provide examples of IMI dataset FAIRification. The platform is a space for developing and hosting documentation and training materials in the form of 'recipes' that consolidate the key steps of procedures used for FAIRification.

4.3. ECRIN Metadata Repository

The Clinical Research [Metadata Repository](#) developed by the European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network ([ECRIN](#)), aims to establish a single, searchable database where metadata about all the data

objects created by clinical research is gathered in one place. This means collecting metadata about data objects (not the data objects themselves) from a variety of sources – trial registries, bibliographic system, data repositories, etc. – and in a variety of forms, together with some basic data on the studies themselves. The harvested data is then transformed into a consistent metadata schema, in a single data store, and that store is then available for querying through search and filter mechanisms in a web portal.

The MDR is still under active development, but currently holds about 600,000 study records and 900,000 data object records. The intention is to develop additional APIs around the data and extend the numbers of source data repositories. Data and other data objects from paediatric studies are not specifically identified within the MDR (at the moment) but are included and searchable along with all other data sources.

4.4 Rare 2030 Policy Recommendations

Designing and implementing activities to make paediatric clinical trial data more FAIR are very much in-line with recent recommendations issued in the rare disease field (which, as above, shares a lot of common ground with the paediatric community). The political and cultural context around data sharing and reuse is an important backdrop here.

Rare 2030¹⁵ (2019-2021) was a foresight study requested by the European Parliament and supported by the European Commission to gather the input of a broad rare disease community and propose policy recommendations¹⁶ that will lead to improved policy and a better future for people living with a rare disease in Europe in the next 10 years and beyond.

The project ended with a major policy conference in Rare Disease Week 2021, presenting a set of future-facing recommendations on the most critical areas requiring robust policies. The recommendations are presented across 8 interlinked chapters, and together address a very broad range of topics. Several chapters are relevant to this work and include many action-focused recommendations to guide Europe towards the future the rare disease field most wishes to see.

The document is centred around fundamental overarching recommendations. The key recommendation number 7, pertaining to data, is as follows:

*All European data sources of relevance to addressing the challenges faced by people living with rare diseases should be federated in a continuum encompassing epidemiological, healthcare, research, quality of life and treatment-related data, and should be linked at the global level where possible. **Sharing of data for care and research should be optimised across infrastructures and countries**, relying upon commonly adopted codification systems (Orphanet nomenclature), harmonised standards and interoperability requirements.*

*Cohesive data ecosystems should be developed at national level, linking seamlessly via **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) data approaches** to an integrated European*

¹⁵ <https://www.rare2030.eu>

¹⁶ <https://www.rare2030.eu/recommendations/>

*ecosystem, positioned within the European Health Data Space and centred on robust ERNs, the European Platform on Rare Disease Registration, and other key infrastructures. Legal and ethical guidelines and regulations should incentivise practices that best lead to addressing these challenges while respecting international, national and regional laws and conventions – particularly **the preferences and privacy of people living with rare diseases and their families.***

The following recommendations from this chapter, in particular, support the work undertaken in c4c WP5:

From the chapter on ‘Optimising Data for Patient and Societal Benefit’ (p100-110):

- Consensus should be developed at the European - and ideally global - level, to identify and agree the most appropriate standards and ontologies for all types of data, addressing not only diagnoses and phenotypes but also treatments, quality of life, and more: these standards should be henceforth used for public and private data generated at source, including clinical (health and social sector) and research level (including registries and data repositories) data; (p104)
- European and national authorities should promote the implementation of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data principles, particularly for rare disease data: they should:
 - Provide incentives which favour data sharing or at least shareability, with a standard requirement to share data from publicly-funded research - such as placebo data and data from failed trials - to inform and streamline future research: companies should be encouraged to act similarly, whilst respecting IPR
 - Invest in training expert data stewards able to advise stakeholders in the national territory on FAIR-compliant data management and to support individual research projects or clinical trials in preparing relevant data from the outset, for potential secondary use in future, capitalising on the experienced achieved by the European Joint Programme for Rare Diseases

The chapter on ‘Innovative and Needs-Led Research and Development’ (p87-99) also contains some very relevant action-focused recommendations:

- Research pertaining to communities with natural synergies to rare diseases must be conducted collaboratively: in particular, cross-talk and collaboration in the paediatric sphere must be ensured between European Joint Programme for Rare Diseases and Conect4Children, and all relevant future organisations (p91)
- Research funders should insist upon greater reproducibility of data, for all stages of rare disease research, and should follow leading publications by increasingly assessing the robustness of strategies for data management, interoperability, reproducibility and sharing/ linkage when evaluating proposals (p92)
- There should be a requirement to share data (at a minimum metadata) from publicly-funded research, once complete, to inform and streamline future research: patient organisations and Industry should be encouraged to act similarly, whilst respecting intellectual property rights (p92)
- Researchers should be encouraged and incentivised to publish data from ‘failed’ basic or clinical research; companies must publish data from ‘failed’ clinical research, to inform future research (p92)
- FAIR data stewardship should be available to support individual research projects or clinical trials in preparing relevant data from the outset, for potential secondary use in future - the costs for this should be included in the initial funding proposal, to ensure all results are FAIR-compliant (p93)

The chapter on patient partnerships (p75-86) also contains pertinent principles and good practices concerning research in rare diseases (and by extension, paediatric diseases). The Rare 2030 project was coordinated by EURORDIS and actively supported by key c4c partners Newcastle University, MetabERN and ERN BOND.

4.5. EURORDIS data collection to illustrate patient perspectives on data sharing and protection

[EURORDIS](#), through its Rare Barometer Voices programme, is perfectly placed to design and conduct large surveys of people living with a rare disease, both in Europe and at a global level. In January 2020, the results of a survey on ‘Rare disease patients’ preferences on data sharing and protection’ were published.¹⁷

This sort of information is extremely valuable in designing activities to support the reuse of personal data such as clinical trial data and is informing the FAIR data working group as well as the other components of WP5 of c4c. For example, 97% of patients surveyed were prepared to share their data to develop new treatments for their disease, with 95% of respondents willing to share their data to advance research for diseases other than their own.

4.6. Select existing initiatives and papers

Initiative/Paper	Link	Description
FAIRPlus Cookbook	https://fairplus.github.io/the-fair-cookbook/content/home.html	The platform is a space for developing and hosting documentation and training materials in the form of ‘recipes’ that consolidate the key steps of procedures used for FAIRification.
De-novo FAIRification of registries	https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.12.12.20245951v1.full.pdf	Describes the five-step process of making a rare disease registry FAIR from its conception.
De-novo FAIRification via an Electronic Data Capture System	https://www.medrxiv.org/content/10.1101/2021.03.04.21250752v1.full.pdf	Describes the development of a novel method for de-novo FAIRification via an EDC system.
FAIR4Health: From Raw Data to	https://www.thieme-	Proposes a workflow and

¹⁷ <https://www.eurordis.org/publication/share-and-protect-our-health-data-rare-disease-patients-preferences-data-sharing-and-protection>

FAIR Data: The FAIRification Workflow for Health Research	connect.de/products/ejournals/abstract/10.1055/s-0040-1713684	technical architecture to FAIRify health care datasets resulting from health research.
VASCA Codebook	https://vascern.eu/ejp-rd-tool-for-fairification-of-patient-registries-made-for-the-vasca-registry-now-available-for-use/ https://decor.nictiz.nl/art-decor/decor-datasets--vasca-?id=&effectiveDate=&conceptId=&conceptEffectiveDate=	A rare disease registry codebook that contains the mappings of the common data elements (CDEs) to ontologies and brings together the definition (for humans) as well as the identifiers/code used in the EJP RD CDEs Semantic Model to annotate each data element (for computers), increasing interoperability of data.
Pistoia Alliance FAIR Toolkit	https://fairtoolkit.pistoiaalliance.org/	The FAIR Toolkit provides use cases for better understanding the importance of FAIR and tools, training, and change management to implement the FAIR guidelines.
Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things - Biomedical Data Producers, Stewards, and Funders	https://librarycarpentry.org/Top-10-FAIR/2018/12/01/biomedical-data-producers/	This provides brief training at beginner and intermediate level to better understand FAIRification of data and software in the biomedical domain.
LOINC	https://loinc.org/get-started/what-loinc-is/	A major area of added value would be to standardise the reporting of lab results, for instance through better deployment of LOINC. This is being employed in an industry or healthcare provision context where lab information can then be exchanged across systems based on agreed upon vocabularies.

5. Next Steps

This document has outlined the rationale for exploring how to make paediatric clinical trial data more FAIR. It has explained what the main principles can mean, when applied to this domain. It highlights relevant resources already created or else in development within c4c, and also showcases numerous initiatives, assets and papers developed outside of c4c, which may be considered very relevant to the design and

implementation of the work of the c4c FAIR data working group. Each existing resource has been assessed to show its potential to meet the FAIR principles. Most importantly, it presents a methodology to develop more technical guidance and recommendations on how to FAIRify CRFs for paediatric clinical trials, bearing in mind the state of the art of FAIRification efforts across various domains.

The plan to conduct more focused, practical work on real-life CRFs was outlined, and the results of this analysis will inform an updated future version of this document, delivered as a guide for trial developers. This next phase will foreseeably include FAIRPlus collaborators, to broaden the reach and impact of the recommendations.

For further discussion on this subject, contact unew_imi2team@newcastle.ac.uk